

Business Model Development Tools: Plan for Organisational Success

Writer: Damianos Michailidis

Organisation: RAINNO

Keywords: Business Models, b=Business Strategy, Business Model Tools

“Business model tools are commonly used to describe and communicate business model ideas” [1] and are conceptualised, in research, as boundary objects that are meant to make possible the exchange of information between, often disparate in nature, stakeholders [2]. For the purpose of this article, Business Models Tools are defined as *“the use of methods, frameworks or templates (here referred to as tools) to facilitate communication and collaboration regarding Business Model analysis, (re-)design, adoption, implementation and exploitation”* [3].

In the framework of the [XGain project](#), which aims to provide innovative business models regarding connectivity solutions in European rural areas, a vital part of the process was to analyse various business model tools in order to choose the best one to tackle the 6 different project use cases in the sectors of agriculture, aquaculture, forestry, e-Health and tourism.

Business Models Tools Overview

A **business model tool** provides a quick overview of the business model including all crucial elements of a business and existing relations between them. While looking for the best suited business model tool for the **XGain’s** use cases, a comprehensive analysis of business model tools that are widely used and that can be applied in the context of the XGain project was conducted. Those tools were the following: *Business Model Canvas* [4]; *Lean Startup Canvas* [5]; *Value Proposition Canvas* [6]; *Business Model Radar* [7] and *Prototyping Canvas* [8].

Presenting a short overview of the analysis, it can be said that, many companies worldwide use Business Model Canvas as a compact and clear guideline for their businesses, but when it comes to new/small companies Lean Startup Canvas is a more suited option because it includes startup factors such as uncertainty and risk. Another business model tool that is especially recommended to startups is Value Proposition Canvas. It helps businesses to create a perfect fit between their products and market. The Business Model Radar places a strong emphasis on providing services as the core value proposition and revenue generator for the organisation and it is the proposed framework for business modelling of Data Spaces. This approach contrasts with traditional product-centred models where tangible goods are the primary focus. When an organisation is still in the phase of product development, Prototyping Canvas can help with testing a certain aspect of the developing product or service. It effectively guides designers through prototyping processes and facilitates a common prototyping language amongst team members.

XGain Business Model Tool Selection

In the context of XGain and the digital connectivity in remote areas, **the Business Model Canvas** was decided to be the business modelling tool of choice, in order to gain a deeper understanding and propose the right business models for the project relevant sectors and services. This tool offers the

possibility of a more extensive approach compared to others and enables a greater level of complexity and detail to be incorporated. The approach promotes a collaborative team dynamic by involving all stakeholders and encouraging active participation in the development, enhancement, and fine-tuning of the business models. This framework is versatile and can be customised to suit diverse business types, industries, and customer segments.

The following list includes a number of reasons why the Business Model Canvas is a suitable option for the XGain project:

- **Simplicity and Clarity:** XGain use cases are placed in remote areas involving various stakeholders and complex ecosystems. The simplicity and visual clarity of the Business Model Canvas can help clearly define and communicate the different components of a digital connectivity initiative.
- **Comprehensive View:** The canvas covers various aspects of a business model, including key partners, customer segments, value propositions, and revenue streams. When working on digital connectivity in remote areas, we need to consider multiple elements, such as infrastructure, technology, partnerships, and customer needs. The canvas helps ensure we address all relevant aspects.
- **Value Proposition:** One of the critical elements of the Business Model Canvas is the value proposition. Understanding the unique value of digital connectivity, through the use cases, provided to communities or businesses in these remote locations is crucial. The canvas helps to define and refine the value proposition.
- **Partnerships and Resources:** In the context of remote connectivity, partnerships with local authorities, technology providers, and community organisations may be essential. The canvas allows you to identify and visualise these key partnerships and the resources required for each use case.
- **Cost Structure:** Operating in remote areas can come with unique cost challenges. The canvas enables us to outline and manage the cost structure effectively, helping us identify areas where cost optimization is necessary.
- **Customer Segments:** Understanding the specific needs and preferences of people or businesses in remote areas is vital. The Business Model Canvas encourages to define the customer segments, which can lead to more targeted and effective solutions.
- **Quick Iteration:** The canvas facilitates rapid iteration and experimentation, allowing us to make adjustments to our business model as needed.

There is not one correct or better way to create a business model, but several different processes and tools that can all produce valid results depending on the situation. In the complex landscape of rural digital connectivity, the XGain project strategically opts for the Business Model Canvas. Serving as a clear communicator, the canvas navigates remote challenges, providing a comprehensive view of partnerships, costs, and customer segments. In the framework of the project, it's not just a tool but a versatile and essential instrument, painting the landscape of possibilities for successful digital connectivity solutions and increasing the competitiveness and sustainability of rural communities.

References

1. Athanasopoulou, A., & De Reuver, M. (2020). How do business model tools facilitate business model exploration? Evidence from action research. *Electronic Markets*, 30, 495-508.
2. Bouwman, H., Heikkilä, J., Heikkilä, M., Leopold, C., & Haaker, T. (2018). Achieving agility using business model stress testing. *Electronic Markets*, 28, 149-162.
3. Bouwman, H., De Reuver, M., Heikkilä, M., & Fielt, E. (2020). Business model tooling: where research and practice meet. *Electronic Markets*, 30(3), 413-419.
4. Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2010). *Business model generation: a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers* (Vol. 1). John Wiley & Sons.
5. Simanjuntak, M., Banjarnahor, A. R., Handiman, U. T., Permadi, L. A., Murdana, I. M., Nasrullah, N., ... & Patiung, M. (2022). *Perancangan Model Bisnis Pariwisata*. Yayasan Kita Menulis.
6. Clark, T., Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y. *Business Model You: A One-Page Method For Reinventing Your Career*, Wiley, London, 2012. 264 p., ISBN: 978-1118156315.
7. Turetken, O., & Grefen, P. (2017). *Designing service-dominant business models*.
8. Lauff, C., Menold, J., & Wood, K. L. (2019, July). Prototyping canvas: Design tool for planning purposeful prototypes. In *Proceedings of the design society: international conference on engineering design* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 1563-1572). Cambridge University Press.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA) (granting authority). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.